

European Public Local Authorities' Network for
driving the Energy Transition

D3.1 - ePLANET platform specifications

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Executive Summary

The ePLANET project is a Coordination and Support Action cofounded by the European Commission through Horizon 2020. The ePLANET aims to deploy new clustering governance for an energy transition based on a digital framework to share harmonised information, facilitating the adoption of coordinated energy transition actions by the European public sector.

This document is the first of four within the WP3: Digitalization. It presents the ePLANET platform specifications. In addition, this document explains the technical and non-technical requirements that constrained the platform, which analytical outputs are expected and how they will be presented in all the ePLANET federated platform modules.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

ABBREVIATION OR ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
API	Application Programming Interface
BEI	Baseline Emissions Inventory
CapEx	Capital expenditures
CoM	Covenant of Mayors
DNSH	Do Not Significantly Harm
ECM	Energy Conservation Measure
EPC	Energy Performance Certificate
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIS	Geographic Information System
IT	Information Technology
JRC	Joint Research Centre
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MEI	Monitoring Emissions Inventory
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
OpEx	Operational expenditures
PA	Public Authority
PV	Photovoltaics
SEAP	Sustainable energy action plan
SECAP	Sustainable energy action and climate plan
toe	Tonne of oil equivalent
UC	Use Case
UDTM	Unified Digital Technical Map

1 Introduction to the ePLANET project

The ePLANET project is a Coordination and Support Action co-funded by the European Commission through Horizon 2020 program. This project aims at deploying **new clustering governance** for an energy transition based on a digital framework to share harmonised information, facilitating the adoption of coordinated energy transition actions by the European public sector.

The development of ePLANET aims to boost the Energy Transition (ET) in the public sector. The main challenges are:

- Improving coordination between local authorities and regional governments,
- Enhancing the decision-making process in the deployment of ET projects,
- Providing coherence and consistency to the Energy Transition Measures (ETM) to be implemented,
- Encouraging the digitalisation of ET measures and plans,
- Enabling an interoperable ecosystem of data and tools.

All these targeted objectives will support the energy transition decision-making process and its practical implementation.

This document defines the ePLANET platform specifications. The deliverable starts with a summary of the technical and non-technical requirements of the platform. Then, it describes the output data requirements by each use case indicating the data sources. Therefore, it represents the architecture used in the federated ePLANET architecture focusing on the communication layers and the databases used. Finally, this deliverable describes how the platform is implemented in each specific use case and pilot site.

2 ePLANET platform requirements

2.1 Technical requirements

2.1.1 Federated and open platform

ePLANET project will implement three everyday use cases which will be customised for three different pilot sites. The main priority, from a technical point of view, is to keep a standard ICT architecture able to include all the necessary analytical modules to assure seamless interoperability among the different components. Besides, some of the visualisation interfaces will be implemented by an external contractor which will provide its proprietary framework. Under these circumstances, and based on the experience gained in previous research and development projects, the best solution is to constitute a federated architecture.

Federated architecture as database architecture was first introduced by Denis Heimbigner 1982¹ and 1985² with the title: A Federated Architecture for Information Management:^[4] "This federated database architecture allows a collection of database systems (components) to unite into a loosely coupled federation in order to share and exchange information. In recent years, the term federation was broadened as:

Federated architecture is a pattern that unifies semi-autonomous applications, networks, or software systems. Each system ("state") operates semi-autonomously. It can scale, process, experiment, and implement different technology. However, it complies with the rules that allow it to exist symbiotically with other related systems ("Union").

Holding the entities together is the **central operating model**. This model exists on a spectrum between two extremes: strong and weak. Intuitively, an architect may design for more top-level control (strong) or give more power to the lower-level entities (weak).

2.1.2 Functional requirements

At the beginning of the ePLANET project, CIMNE (the technical responsible of the ePLANET platform), had several meetings with the pilot site leaders (DDGI, RDFC and EAZK) to define the main functional requirements of the platform. A summary of these requirements, as a conclusion of these meetings, is listed below:

- In the Spanish pilot case: ePLANET platform should be compatible with the CoM/MENAE reporting form. It should also include the following capacities:
 - Possibility to export CoM/MENAE compatible Excels directly from the digital tool
 - Possibility of reading the information directly from previously created CoM/MENAE Excels and filling in the fields in digital tool's database
- The ePLANET platform should be compatible with the EU taxonomy input data formats

¹ Heimbigner, D. M. *A federated architecture for database systems*. Ph.D. dissertation, Univ. of Southern California, Los Angeles, California, August 1982

² Heimbigner, Dennis and McLeod, Dennis, *A Federated Architecture for Information Management*, 1985.

- The ePLANET platform should be able to generate a database of mitigation actions with possibility to:
 - Evaluate the impact of the implemented energy transition measures (linking them to the monitoring of the progress on emission reduction pledges)
 - Give possibility to the municipalities to access to visualisation interfaces of the measures implemented by other participant municipalities based on similarity criteria (geographical proximity, weather, number of inhabitants, economic and census data, etc.)
- Easy access to the assessment of risks and vulnerabilities to climate change impacts for specific regions.
- Facilitate the process of creating the baseline emission inventory (BEI) for the pilot cases of Spain and Greece:
 - Through direct API connection to the data sources where possible (Datadis, Negdia, ICAEN, CORES, REE etc.)
 - Automated fuel and emission conversion calculations
 - Clear differentiation between mandatory and optional fields according to the Covenant of Mayors (COM) agreement.
- Possibility to access custom analytics and KPIs that facilitate the comparison of pledges, goals, implemented strategies, assigned budget, expected and achieved impact of measures.
- Possibility to highlight Benchmarks of Excellence
- Possibility to visualise on a GIS based visualisation platform:
 - BEI and MEI (individual fields or aggregated)
 - Avoided emissions
 - Regions where specific measures have been applied
 - Renewable energy communities
 - Custom analytics (emissions/inhabitants, emissions/m², kWh produced of carbon neutral energy, energy transition expenditure/inhabitant etc.)

2.2 Input data requirements

The input data requirements are conditioned to the data availability of the three pilot regions. Therefore, the three pilot regions answered a survey related to the different information they could provide to identify these available data. These surveys requested the following data and their granularity:

- Electricity consumption.
- Natural gas consumption.
- Biomass consumption.
- Liquid fuels consumption.
- Studies of RES potential.
- Installed RES power.
- Installed RES energy generation.
- Transport and mobility data.
- Implemented SECAPs.
- Monitoring data from the municipal buildings.
- Cadastre data.
- Urban infrastructure.
- GIS mapped information.

- Land use category.
- Socioeconomic data.

The summary of the surveys is in Tables 2-1 to 2-3.

Table 2-1 Crete Island pilot data availability

Data entry	Municipal level	Provincial level	Regional level	National level	Granularity
Electricity consumption in buildings	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Municipal/regional buildings: typically, monthly and annual data, National level: annual data
Natural gas consumption in buildings	No	No	No	No	Municipal/regional buildings: typically, monthly and annual data, National level: annual data
Energy use in waste management	No	No	No	Yes	Monthly / annual. Some SECAPs provide information for the baseline year but most municipalities can't share monthly data
RES installation data (installed kW)	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	n/a
RES generation data (generated kWh)	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	n/a
Studies of RES potential	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Monthly / annual
Transport and mobility data	No	No	Yes	Yes	Some SECAPs provide information for the baseline year but most municipalities can't share monthly data
Implemented SEAP/SECAP data and their estimated/calculated impact	Yes	No	No	No	One-off data in SEAPs, obligation for monitoring report every two years
Monitoring data from buildings (occupancy, implemented ECMs, building use, energy efficiency certificates)	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Annual energy consumption displayed on EPCs. Only a tiny share of buildings, usually major/emblematic buildings in each municipality have EPCs. Not all municipal/regional and generally public buildings have EPCs yet.

Cadastre data (i.e. floor area, number of stories for public and private buildings)	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	n/a Based on the availability of relevant data on the GIS or other open access data.
Urban Infrastructure	Yes	No	No	Yes	n/a It depends on the elements of urban infrastructure (i.e. public lighting, is available)
GIS mapped information	Yes	No	No		n/a
Land use categories	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	n/a
Socio-economic data	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	n/a

Table 2-2 Girona Province pilot data availability

Data entry	Municipal level	Provincial level	Regional level	National level	Description	Granularity
Electricity consumption in buildings	Yes	No	No	No	Yearly electricity at municipality level.	Yearly
Natural gas consumption in buildings	Yes	No	No	No	Yearly gas at municipality level.	Yearly
Biomass consumption in buildings	Yes	No	No	No	Yearly biomass at municipality level	Yearly
Fuel consumption in buildings	Yes	No	No	No	Yearly fuel for buildings heating at municipality level	Yearly
Fuel consumption in mobility	Yes	No	No	No	Yearly fuel for transport and mobility at municipality level	Yearly
Energy use in waste management	Yes	No	No	No	Energy used for the collection of municipal waste.	Yearly
RES installation data (installed kW)	Yes	No	No	No		
RES generation data (generated kWh)	Yes	No	No	No		
Studies of RES potential	No	No	No	No	Feasibility studies for PV and wind installation in the Girona region.	
Transport and mobility data	Yes	No	No	No	Yearly data on fossil fuel consumption by municipality.	Yearly

Implemented SEAP/SECAP data and their estimated/calculated impact	Yes	No	No	No	
Monitoring data from buildings (occupancy, implemented ECMs, building use, energy efficiency certificates)	Yes	No	No	No	Building use, hourly energy consumption, implemented ECMs, and energy efficiency certificates for public buildings.
Cadastre data (i.e. floor area, number of stories for public and private buildings)	Yes	No	No	No	Floor area, year of construction, number of stories.
Urban Infrastructure	No	No	No	No	
GIS mapped information	No	No	Yes	No	
Land use categories	No	No	Yes	No	
Socioeconomic data	Yes	No	No	No	Income by postal code for different municipalities.

Table 2-3 Zlín Region pilot data availability

Data entry	Municipal level	Provincial level	Regional level	National level	Description	Granularity
Electricity consumption in buildings	Yes	No	Yes	No	app. 70 municipalities and all organisations established by the Zlín Region	monthly data from end user's delivery points
Natural gas consumption in buildings	Yes	No	Yes	No	app. 40 municipalities and all organisations established by the Zlín Region	monthly data from end user's delivery points
Energy use in waste management	No	No	Yes	No	waste incinerator combusting hospital waste with an actual capacity of 300 tons/year	Daily consumption of waste and produced heat
RES installation data (installed kW)	Yes	No	Yes	No	1909 licenced energy producers that generate electricity and heat - mostly PVE installations (1800)	Name, address, number of licences, installed power
RES generation data (generated kWh)	Yes	No	Yes	No	2 PVE in Uherské hradiště hospital; FVE in Horní Němčí (municipality); biomass DH systems in	Daily production of electricity from PVE on hospital

					Slavičín (municipality) a Brumov Bylnice (municipality)	installations and monthly on municipal installations
Studies of RES potential	No	No	Yes	No	Study on Short rotation crops from 2015 only	
Transport and mobility data	No	No	Yes	Yes	Data from mobility are gathered only for emissions (Czech hydrometeorological institute) and GIS maps on a national level.	National level
Implemented SEAP/SECAP data and their estimated/calculated impact	No	No	No	No	SECAPs not implemented in the complex form outlined by CoM or similar.	
Monitoring data from buildings (occupancy, implemented ECMs, building use, energy efficiency certificates)	Yes	No	Yes	No	All buildings that have been involved in OP Environment projects submitted by EAZK for both the Zlín Region and municipalities since the year 2018	buildings - consumption of natural gas or heat from district heating system, electricity, water, ECM
Cadastral data (i.e. floor area, number of stories for public and private buildings)	Yes	No	Yes	No	Data consisting of a number of the parcel, number of the building, area m ² , owner, restrictions	building by building
Urban Infrastructure	Yes	No	No	No	EAZK, in cooperation with the Zlín Region, obtained shapefiles of the Zlín Region and Lidar data from the whole region. Shapefiles describe not only the shape of the building but also, for example, the number of floors, height, type of heating, number of apartments, etc. The data administrator for the Czech Republic is the State Administration of Surveying and Cadastre (https://www.cuzk.cz/)	-----

GIS mapped information	Yes	No	Yes	No	"UDTM - Unified Digital Technical Map" - Tool for externalisation of present built-up areas of towns and villages, including underground and above-ground engineering networks	
Land use categories	Yes	No	Yes	No	Data are provided for all agricultural fields and places	each agricultural field allocated in cadastre
Socioeconomic data	No	No	Yes	No	Only on a regional level. A yearly published book by the Czech statistical office focuses only on the Zlín region. Collected data:	regional level

2.3 Output data requirements

The ePLANET platform should be able to interact with some external reporting services which will determine the format of the outputs to be exported from the platform. In the following sections, a brief description of these external reporting services is presented.

2.3.1 MENAE reporting (Girona region pilot site)

In the MENAE (Mecanismo de ENvío de Ahorros Energéticos) reporting, there is no baseline inventory emission. The report should be written in Excel format and the focus is on the implemented measures/strategies. Specific criteria should be met:

- The goal of this Excel file is to report, for each grant, initiative, or action, the yearly energy savings and the avoided emissions linked to that action
- Every line of the Excel represents an action that was taken in the municipality to save energy/reduces emissions.
- The sector which is linked to the action needs to be specified. The available sectors are:
 - Industry
 - Transportation
 - Buildings
 - Public services
 - Agriculture and fishing
- In the description, a match needs to be found between the action and the measures included in the (Plan Nacional de Acción de Eficiencia Energética)
- Additional funds for the specific measures should be also described and quantified in detail.
- A responsible person should be identified within the organisation.
- The total investment linked with the action should be pointed out, making a distinction between:
 - Loans
 - Non-refundable grants
 - Other type of investments, such as a municipality investing for the change of public lighting
- A summary of the number of projects linked with that action (for example, if the action is a grant for the refurbishment of heating systems, how many applications have been received and granted)
- If relevant, the number of refurbished buildings/m² also needs to be pointed out
- Total primary electricity savings associated with the action (toe/year)
- Total primary thermal energy savings related to the action (toe/year)

- Total final energy savings (electricity + thermal, toe/year)
- Total CO2 savings associated with the action (toe/year)

Correspondence between CoM fields and MENAE fields

The MENAE Excel is actually corresponding to one subsection of the SECAP template, the mitigation action section. In the mitigation actions sheets, the ‘key actions’ section contains a list of the planned measures. table of all the fields included in the MENAE Excel, together with the SECAP template fields that could match them, is shown:

MENAE fields	SECAP fields
Nombre de la línea de actuaciones	Key actions
Referencia a disposición administrativa de aprobación de la línea	
Fecha inicio (dd/mm/aa)	Starting date
Fecha fin (dd/mm/aa)	End date
Sector	This information is not represented by a column, but by a row, which separates different sections of the template
Descripción	Description
Cofinanciación (sí/no)	
Descripción cofinanciación	
Otras observaciones	
Nombre persona de contacto	Responsible
Primer apellido persona de contacto	
Segundo apellido persona de contacto	
Teléfono persona de contacto	
E-mail persona de contacto	
Subvención a fondo perdido (€)	
Intensidad ayuda subvención a fondo perdido (%)	
Préstamo reembolsable (€)	Loan
Financiación máxima préstamo reembolsable (%)	
Inversión total (€)	Investment of the action
Número de proyectos	
Número de edificios	Number of buildings
Superficie rehabilitada (m ²)	
Ahorro energía eléctrica (toe/año)	
Ahorro energía térmica (toe/año)	
Ahorro energía total (toe/año)	Final energy consumption saving (MWh/y)
Emisiones evitadas CO ₂ (tCO ₂ /año)	CO ₂ emissions reduction (tCO ₂ /year)

Table 2-4 Comparison of variables of the MENAE and the mitigation section of the SECAP

2.3.2 EU Taxonomy

The EU taxonomy is a green classification system that translates the EU’s climate and environmental objectives into criteria for specific economic activities for investment purposes.

The EU taxonomy is a classification system of “environmentally sustainable economic activities”

It has been created to help investors make green investments. Six environmental objectives have been identified:

Figure 2-1. Scheme of the environmental objectives of the EU taxonomy

The taxonomy specifies how each activity can contribute to each goal. To be taxonomy aligned, an action must contribute to at least one objective, Do No Significant Harm (DNSH) to any of the others, and meet minimum social safeguards.

From 2022, taxonomy rules apply to all large European companies that fall under the NFRD (Non-Financial Reporting Directive); i.e. public interest entities with more than 500 employees. The companies will need to report on the percentage of their overall turnover, CapEx and OpEx in FY'22 that is taxonomy eligible. Financial market participants offering products in the EU that promote environmental objectives are also required to report.

How is the EU taxonomy structured?

The taxonomy looks at a number of major sectors including agriculture, manufacturing, transportation, energy, construction and communications. For each sector, it provides a list of industry-relevant activities that could be considered sustainable.

Figure 2-2. Process flow to check if an action is EU taxonomy aligned

It then looks at each activity through the lens of its six environmental objectives by providing a list of ‘substantial contribution’ criteria and ‘do no significant harm’ (or DNSH) criteria for each objective. For an activity to be considered eligible, it only needs to meet the substantial contribution criteria for one of the six objectives. For it to be taxonomy aligned, it has to meet the substantial contribution criteria for at least one of the six, comply with the DNSH criteria for all six, and meet minimum social and governance safeguards (in accordance with the OECD, UN and ILO issued guidelines).

What needs to be reported? and when?

If taxonomy rules apply to the specific PA, they will need to disclose in their annual report how much of your overall business follows the activities outlined in the taxonomy.

The taxonomy is currently being rolled out in two phases:

1. **In phase 1**, companies need to report on the proportion of their turnover, capital expenditures (CapEx) and operational expenditures (OpEx) that is taxonomy eligible. This phase begins in 2022 (for the 2022 annual report) for financial institutions and all other sectors.
2. **In phase 2**, companies need to report on the proportion of their turnover, CapEx and OpEx that is taxonomy aligned. This phase will begin in 2023 or in 2024 for large companies and financial institutions respectively.

How the ePLANET Energy Transition Measures (ETM) will be EU taxonomy aligned?

The process of checking if the ePLANET ETM are aligned with the EU taxonomy will start once all the mitigation and adaptation actions of the SECAPs of Girona region and Crete Island, as well as all the energy efficient measures to be applied in the public buildings of Zlín region and of Crete Island, are gathered, harmonised and stored into the ePLANET system. A mapping between the ePLANET taxonomy and the EU taxonomy will be performed for each ETM. The alignment checking of each ET, which must contribute to at least one objective, Do No Significant Harm (DNSH) to any of the others, and meet minimum social safeguards, will be also undertake. Specific KPIs related to the EU taxonomy alignment will be included in the visual interfaces of the ePLANET platform.

2.4 Requirements determined by the pilot sites

In months 3 to 6 of the project, several meetings have been carried out among the technical partner (CIMNE) and the responsible of each pilot site region (DDGI, RDFC and EAZK). These meetings led to the definition of the requirements the ePLANET platform should fulfil from the perspective of the pilot site regions. They are summarised in this section.

2.4.1 Zlín region

Status of the pilot site region in relation to the Energy Transition

In Zlín region there are only 3 or 4 PAs with energy transition plans and they are not compliant with CoM. In the region there are no signatories of CoM. On the other hand, EAZK, acting as the regional energy agency is assuming many activities related to the ET in the region. EAZK does not expect newer municipalities joining CoM in the following years. In the region, the PAs do not usually officially join the CoM, although they have many activities related to ET going on.

Regarding the energy sources, the majority of municipalities are connected to the gas pipeline.

Level of digitalisation

All the municipalities which are being assessed by EAZK, have a unified digitally technical map. This technological map includes several layers: water pipelines, gas pipelines, IT network, central heating system pipelines, public lighting networks. This software application is at the digital level. EAZK controls the map and can make modifications. The ePLANET platform should be something separate, no interaction between the ePLANET platform and the map is expected. EAZK will get data from the map for the ePLANET platform, but there will not be any direct communication don't modify it.

Regarding the digitalisation of data not related to that map, EAZK have LIDAR data of the whole region. These data are accessible and can be the basis for the UC 4.

Challenges for the Energy Transition

In the households there are still several local coal-fired boilers. Only in small percentage of municipalities there are central heating systems, using coal as fuel.

Platform specifications

EAZK is interested in implementing the following use cases in their region:

Use-case 2: analysis of energy consumption data of public buildings

- EAZK in possession of monthly electricity, natural gas, and water consumption data for regional municipal and regional public buildings. The ePLANET platform should be able to periodically upload these files, process them and incorporate into the visual interfaces to help EAZK in their energy assessment activities.
- Regarding other relevant information (postal code, building typology, building primary use etc.), it would be possible to obtain it but it would have to be done manually by EAZK staff for each building separately.

Use-case 3: Geo tools for the promotion of energy communities

They're in the process of accessing energy consumption of the whole municipality of Hostetín (best practice example of an environmentally friendly village). By matching this data to LIDAR shapefiles, EAZK could progress in the energy communities use-case.

Use-case 4: PV potential analysis for rooftops

- EAZK is primarily interested in knowing the PV potential of specific buildings, but if it would be possible to map the whole municipality, they wouldn't oppose it.
- It's not easy for them to access LIDAR data shapefiles. Publicly available LIDAR data for viewing only are for the whole Czech Republic [here](#). If ePLANET platform can work with these data so that they don't have to apply for LIDAR shapefiles it would be great.

- Currently, EAZK possess LIDAR data for 5 municipalities, that do not overlap with those included in the ePLANET project.

2.4.2 Crete island

Status of the pilot site region in relation to the Energy Transition

RDFC is the regional coordinator of the CoM and Col (Covenant of Islands). RDFC has a regional Crete support framework, together with the Greek one.

RDFC can activate many financial tools, however, they need for coordination and getting the maximum results from these available resources.

Level of digitalisation

At the present, the digitalisation of SECAPs monitoring is a challenge. RDFC tried to convince municipalities that they need to have shared data bases concerning energy efficiency percentages and other data that will be very precious for the future. Another problem is a lack of continuous municipal commitment and a lack of personnel. There's also a lack of regional solid coordination. There's some lack of commitment and of a clear energy transition plan for the whole island. Another problem is the lack of an official recognition for SECAPs from the Greek government. Despite the fact that there's a legislative obligation to draw a plan, there's no such obligation for having a Transition plan by law.

Challenges for the Energy Transition

Crete island were not connected with the mainland electricity network. Now for 2 months, the Greek government set a small interconnection. There are investment plans to level of interconnection to very high levels. Once this is implemented, it will lead to drastically change in the regional energy policy. The small interconnection has different benefits.

In Crete Island there is a significant percentage of wind farms, biomass boilers, solar thermal collectors, PV systems, passive solar systems, hydro, pump storage (100MW) and shallow geothermal.

The island is structured in 24 municipalities. 18 of them have signed the CoM and 16 have submitted SEAPs or SECAPs. There are 4 regional departments.

Platform specifications

RDFC is interested in UC1 and UC 2 and UC3. In relation to UC1, RDFC can provide monthly electricity consumption of municipal buildings from the 16 municipalities and from the regional government. RDFC is interested in uploading these files into the ePLANET system and to be benefited by a general dashboard which may help them in monitoring the energy performance of the buildings and to get the necessary insights to improve the energy assessment services they are already offering to the municipalities.

The UC 2 has some challenges related to the data access. At present, the 16 municipalities directly upload all the data to the CoM platform but don't provide a backup information to RDFC. Therefore, some procedures to export these data and to upload it into ePLANET platform will have to be searched.

RDFC is interested in visualising the monitoring of the SECAPs and of the energy performance of the public buildings, at municipal level, into their regional GIS system.

2.4.3 Girona province

Status of the pilot site region in relation to the Energy Transition

DDGI is the regional representative of the CoM initiative in the province of Girona. DDGI is leading many initiatives and programs addressed to give support to the municipalities in their energy transition.

Level of digitalisation

In the case of Girona, the historical energy consumption and emissions data at municipal level is going to be upload into the ePLANET system through the official SECAP templates. DDGI contracts external companies to perform the updating (every 2 years) of the SECAP monitoring and these companies are responsible of gathering the data for the emissions inventory and for the action plan included in the SECAPs.

Furthermore, DDGI has processed the necessary agreements with the electricity and gas distribution system operators to get access to monthly electricity and gas consumption of all the buildings with more than 4 energy contracts. Each building block address identified by the DSOs will be matched to the Spanish cadastre thanks to the INSPIRE harmonisation. In this way, it will be possible to match the energy and water consumption values to the building characteristics found in the cadastre. Through the cadastre, it will also be possible to obtain the exact geographical coordinates of a building block, and therefore visualise data related to that block on a map.

More detailed energy consumption data will also be available for buildings belonging to the public administration. For these buildings, the DSOs will disclose hourly energy consumption values, unlocking more advanced analytics

Existing rooftop PV installations will be obtained applying machine learning to satellite data, while rooftop PV production potential data will be imported from an existing study.

Platform specifications

DDGI is interested in UC1 and UC3. In the case of UC1 they are interested in having a platform able to process and visualise all the data coming from the SECAP monitoring process and for all the municipalities of the province (220). This platform should include a public dashboard, some analytic modules and data exporting features.

Regarding UC3, DDGI is interested in a platform able to give the municipalities to design and promote energy communities based on collective PV systems. Besides, with the information provided by the DSOs, DDGI is interested in having support for the decision tools which may help them in better defining the economical instruments to afford the energy transition in the province.

3 Description of the federated ePLANET IT architecture

The goal of the ePLANET platform is to provide digital support to municipalities in the planning, drafting, and monitoring of their sustainable energy transition plans at the different levels: public buildings, SECAP, energy community level.... Concretely, the platform will give users the possibility to:

1. Monitor the progress and effectiveness of existing SECAPs;
2. Consult and contribute to a database of energy transition measures, associated investment, and avoided energy/emissions;
3. Access data visualisations at geographical level that can support municipalities and regions in drafting their energy transition plans

The IT infrastructure of ePLANET is based on open-source Big Data technologies and has been developed over the ENMA architecture³ of CIMNE - BEE Group to boost the analytics response and the scalability, addressing the needs of the project.

This section describes the technological choices and the IT architecture of the ePLANET platform.

3.1 Technologies

3.1.1 Apache Hadoop core

Apache Hadoop⁴ is an open-source framework that allows for the distributed processing of large data sets across clusters of computers using simple programming models. Designed to scale up from single servers to thousands of machines, each offering local computation and storage.

The basic modules of the framework include the Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS) for storing data that provides high-throughput access to application data and the Hadoop MapReduce engine for processing of massive data stored across distributed servers.

Hadoop is a key Big Data technology currently used in the core of most of the distributed and cloud computing applications.

3.1.2 Databases

ePLANET uses a combination of databases capable of managing vast quantities of data, storing the incoming raw data from the different sources as well as the internally harmonised data and the results from the analytical processing.

HBASE⁵ is used for allocating all the incoming data in ePLANET and for storing the timeseries data such as building energy consumption, weather data, etc. HBASE is an open-source, non-

³ <https://www.beegroup-cimne.com/enma-big-data-architecture/>

⁴ Apache Hadoop: <https://hadoop.apache.org>

⁵ HBASE: <https://hbase.apache.org>

relational, distributed database modelled after Google's Bigtable capable to host tables with billions of rows and millions of columns.

Neo4j⁶ is the database used to store the harmonised data following ePLANET's data model. Neo4j is a Graph Database that stores not only the data but also the data relationships. The storage of deeply connected data enables high-speed queries and data retrieval.

MongoDB⁷ is the database used for storing additional information on the execution of operations over the data and the different processes that are launched by the system. This information is used for tracking of the operations and management of necessary corrections in the tasks. MongoDB is a fast and popular database, very scalable and with evolving data schemas. It uses a JSON format to store the documents.

3.1.3 Message broker

Kafka⁸ is a message streaming platform ensuring high-speed and high throughput for transferring and processing data in real time. It is a critical component in the ePLANET platform as it provides the capability to ingest the incoming raw data and to harmonise it in real time. Apache Kafka is open-source software and it is distributed by the Apache Software Foundation.

3.1.4 Graphic User Interface

The web-based Graphical User Interface is the component that allows the users to interact with the ePLANET platform, to introduce data and visualise the analytics results. The component is implemented using Java Spring Framework⁹ for the backend and Angular.js for the frontend.

3.1.5 Container Execution Manager

Kubernetes¹⁰ is a container orchestrator used to manage and scale the applications that are running in it. The ePLANET architecture uses the Kubernetes cluster to allow scalability of applications run on distributed systems and ensures there is no downtime. In the ePLANET Kubernetes supports the Graphic User Interface and the APIs for acquiring data from external systems.

3.1.6 Analytics

The analytics modules are implemented using the Hadoop Architecture using R or Python programming languages. They ensure the data processing and analysis and incorporate machine learning models and statistical analysis that allow the calculation of the different analytics results.

⁶ Neo4j: <https://neo4j.com>

⁷ MongoDB: <https://www.mongodb.com>

⁸ Kafka: <https://kafka.apache.org>

⁹ Spring: <https://spring.io>

¹⁰ Kubernetes: <https://kubernetes.io>

Figure 3-1. Technologies in the ePLANET IT architecture

3.2 Layered architecture

Software architecture refers to the basic structure of any software system and incorporates any aspect that makes a system function and behaves as it should. Architecture encompasses the design of components, relationships between components, as well as the user interactions.

The ePLANET architecture is implemented in several functional layers where each layer is focused on solving one part of the data processing. By using this approach, the architecture can be simplified, and it is easier to identify and correct the problems in each layer.

3.2.1 Description of the layers

Figure 3-2. Layered IT architecture of ePLANET

3.2.2 Process layer

The data injection and harmonisation layer is the one that reads the data from the data sources, structures the data and stores them in the corresponding databases. The data are first obtained through several APIs that gathers and stores them in raw data mode. Then, these data are harmonised and also stored. This process guarantees a copy of the raw data in case there is a need to use them, for example, when the time series are aggregated monthly, but then you need a weekly aggregation. The architecture used for the import and harmonisation of the sources is as follows:

Figure 3-3 Import and harmonisation architecture.

Once the data are stored in the defined architecture (Figure 3-3) the external API communication layer takes the roll of communicating these data from the harmonised database to the different modules of the federated ePLANET architecture.

3.2.3 Storage layer

The storage layer contains the databases that store all the data ingested by the system as well as those generated by the system as analytics results. There are two components belonging to that layer:

1. HBASE

This database is used as a Data Lake for storing all the raw data ingested by the system as it comes from the external systems, without any modification. This is enabled by the capacity of HBASE to store huge data loads in any format. Due to the capability to perform very fast querying for consecutive data sets, HBASE is used in ePLANET also for storing time series data.

2. Neo4j

This database is used for storing the processed, internally harmonised, data for the buildings (UC 2) and results. Neo4j is capable of storing the data in a linked and very well organised way allowing fast retrieval of any database entry together with all its relations

3.2.4 Communication layer

The communication layer comprises the components ensuring the communication between the rest of the layers. This communication is performed using messages.

EPLANET's communication layer consists of two main components:

1. Application Programming Interfaces (APIs), used for communication from and to external data sources.
2. Message broker (Kafka), used for internal communication of big data loads within the IT system in streaming for parallel processing.

3.2.5 Presentation Layer:

The presentation layer consists of the web-based User Interfaces (UI) that enable EPLANET user interaction with the system and visualise the analytic results - benchmarking and other services offered by the platform. In ePLANET, each use case will have a different UI framework:

1. **Use Case 1-Digitalisation of SECAP:** CIMNE has settled an external contract which has been awarded to the company INERGY. ePLANET will communicate with the energy management platform of this company, named SIE (Software of Energy Information), to visualise the results of this use case. This UI framework includes several dashboards to show the BEI, the mitigation and adaptation actions at different aggregated levels. It also consists of a "landscape unit" observatory which enables a comparative visualisation of the SECAPs of all the municipalities belonging to the specific region.
2. **Use Case 2- Analysis of the energy performance of public buildings:** CIMNE has settled an external contract which has been awarded to the company INERGY. ePLANET will communicate with the energy management platform of this company, named SIE (Software of Energy Information), to visualise the results of this use case. This UI framework includes several dashboards to show historic benchmarking of the building, comparative benchmarking and specific KPIs. It also consists of a "landscape unit" observatory and the citizen portal which both allow general citizen to be aware of the energy consumption of the public sector at municipal level.
3. **Use case 3- Geo tools for the promotion of energy communities:** This use case applies at the 3 pilot sites. In the case of Girona province, the UI will communicate with their own GIS system (SITMUN). A balance between the information shown in this platform and the one which can be shown in other ePLANET visual interfaces (GIS provided by CIMNE or by external partners), which be agreed in the operation phase. In the case of Crete, all the outcomes will be integrated into their GIS platform. In the case of Zlín, the information related to the buildings will be shown through the same visual interfaces of UC2.
4. **Use case 4-PV potential analysis for public buildings:** The UI of this use case, which only concerns the Zlín region, will be a GIS visualisation framework and will be integrated in the ePLANET visualisation interfaces.

3.3 Hardware requirements

In this section we will define the hardware requirements to implement the different parts of the architecture.

3.3.1 Hadoop Cluster

1. Edge node X1
 - 2 cores
 - 8 GB RAM
 - 50/100 GB SSD
2. Master Nodes X2
 - 4 cores
 - 16 GB RAM
 - 100/300 GB SSD
3. Worker Nodes x6
 - 4 cores
 - 60 GB RAM
 - 500/1000 GB SSD

3.3.2 Database Cluster

Data base node (1 master, 2 replicas) X 3:

- 3 cores
- 16 GB RAM
- 300/1000 GB SSD

3.3.3 Kubernetes

Master X1:

- 4 cores
- 16 GB RAM
- 100/300 GB SSD

Nodes X3:

- 4 cores
- 16 GB RAM
- 100/300 GB SSD

3.4 Software Organisation.

To reuse the software code and maintain a good structure on the different scripts, the analytics modules and the main software code will be structured in the following way:

1. Libraries

The functions that can be used in many different parts of the ePLANET project must be implemented in a library, so we don't have to maintain different versions of this in the projects. These libraries can be uploaded at Git, setting the version commit with a "#TAG", this way we can set the version of the library for each module, and make sure that if modifications are made in more newer versions of the library, will not affect the already installed modules. These libraries will be created as expected for the two main languages used (R and Python).

2. Data analytics' scripts

Each module (ETL, MODEL, BENCHMARKING) will be placed in a different GIT allowing to set additional configuration parameters for each module. This way, if we need the same module in an additional action, or service, we can just use the same code.

4 Digitalisation of SECAP drafting and monitoring process (UC1)

This use case will be dedicated to monitoring the progress of active energy transition plans. Initially, access to this platform section will be restricted to the PA of the pilot sites participating in the project's first stage. They will be able to upload all the relevant data about their active SECAPs. At a second stage, these PA will also have the option to open this information to the general public so that citizens and other interested stakeholders can consult it and receive updates about the goals achieved and the ongoing energy transition efforts.

4.1 Data input and platform requirements

The ePLANET federated IT platform will be prepared to automatically map and upload Baseline Emissions Inventory (BEI) and Monitoring Emissions Inventory (MEI) data of the municipalities and a breakdown of their energy transition campaigns. In addition, specific mitigation and adaptation actions taken until now or planned according to their SECAPs will also be able to be uploaded. The automatic upload will use two data sources: i) the official CoM (Covenant of Mayors) SECAP template of each municipality or land scape unit; ii) the excel files periodically exported by the JRC for all the EU municipalities which already submitted a SECAP¹¹.

The SECAP progress will be monitored on two different levels:

- On a qualitative level, public administrations will be given the possibility to specify and periodically update the status of completion of each of their planned energy transition measures (not started, started, ongoing, advanced state, completed).
- On a quantitative level, the SECAP progress will be monitored through the analysis of different KPIs that can be built by considering available data, such as the energy transition measures taken, the associated budget, and the consumption/emissions reduction in the sectors which are linked to the analysed measures.

The theoretical emissions reduction values included in the SECAPs can then be periodically compared with the actual reduction achieved according to the MEI data, and data-backed decisions can be made to adjust the plans and ensure that targets and pledges are met. In the case of transition measures for which information with higher granularity might be available (e.g., improvement of energy efficiency in public buildings, renovation of the public transport fleet, etc.), it will also be possible to specify the measured savings calculated using other measurement and verification techniques.

Moreover, the SECAP data from all the European municipalities could be uploaded to the platform because the European Joint Research Centre (JRC) is now making public the SECAPs data except for the action's investments. In this way, many KPIs can be benchmarked among all the European municipalities. This database is updated approximately every 6 months. If

¹¹ Baldi, Marta; Tsemekidi tzeiranaki , Sofia; Bertoldi , Paolo; Franco de Los Rios, Camilo; Melica, Giulia ; Treville, Aldo; Clemente, Massimo; kakoulaki, Georgia (2021): GCoM - MyCovenant, 2021, First release. European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC) [Dataset] PID: <http://data.europa.eu/89h/86ec3e42-f8e1-4cdb-a953-d396251d2029>

the pilot regions want the platform to be updated as the SECAPs are uploaded to the CoM platform, the data can be updated from the SECAPs excel. Instead, the data will be gathered from the JRC database, together with all the European municipalities' data, and the investment on each action will be collected from the provided SECAPs excels.

4.2 Data analytic modules

The data analytics services are going to provide indicators in order to classify and determine the energy consumption trends of municipalities and buildings. For this, the SECAP digitalisation use case study is going to present different indicators on the energy consumption of the municipalities and how this energy is consumed:

- Annual energy consumption.
- Annual CO₂ emissions.
- Last year yearly energy consumption.
- Percentage of energy increase or decrease comparing previous year (12-24 month ago) with actual year (0 to 12 month ago).
- Monthly energy consumption of last year.
- Monthly energy consumption of last year by energy source.
- Parentage of energy consumption in buildings increase or decrease comparing last year with actual year.
- Parentage of energy consumption in street lighting increase or decrease comparing last year with actual year.
- Position in the ranking of all the European municipalities in low energy consumption by habitant.

4.3 Visual interfaces for Digitalization of SECAP drafting and monitoring process (UC1)

The tool of the SECAP digitalisation is shown in Figures 5-1 to 5-4. In these figures, present the energy consumption of the municipality buildings and also the CO₂ emissions. Moreover, in Figure 4-3 is ranked the energy efficiency indicators along different municipalities.

Figure 4-1 Overview of public buildings energy consumption at municipal level

Figure 4-2 Overview on the municipality buildings energy consumption along the year.

Figure 4-3 Energy consumption comparison between different municipalities.

Figure 4-4 Historical yearly energy consumption by source and global energy consumption

5 Analysis of the energy performance of the public building stock (UC2)

This module of the ePLANET platform will be a database of public building energy consumption and actuations applied to them. This database is targeting public administrations and other relevant stakeholders looking for data that can back the effectiveness of different actuations and management strategies used on public buildings. Also, it will allow to benchmark the buildings in the platform to compare their energy efficiency.

5.1 Data input and platform requirements

This database will be fed by the building consumption data provided by the corresponding administration registered to the platform. Users will be able to filter the measures by typology, as well as compound metrics such as the ratio between avoided emissions and total investment.

In this UC the Crete Island and the Zlín region will provide excel files with the building static information like the location and the building identification and the measurements of energy consumption.

Upon reaching full-scale, municipalities and regions at European level will be able to use this database of measures to take decisions backed by data when developing their own energy transition plans.

5.2 Data analytic modules

From the analysis of the energy performance of the public building stock module, the following indicators are provided in order to evaluate the energy consumption of the buildings:

- Aggregated energy consumption and other KPIs of public buildings at municipal level.
- A table of buildings of each involved municipality showing all their energy consumption by energy source.
- Historical energy consumption of each building.
- Aggregated energy consumption by energy source and month.
- Comparison of each energy source consumption by month with the previous years' energy consumption on the same month.
- Comparison of monthly water consumption with the previous years' water consumption on the same month.
- Evolution of global energy consumption.
- Evolution of global energy consumption by gross floor area.

Furthermore, the following more advanced data analytics modules will be also implemented:

- Visualise the energy performance of their buildings
- Visualise KPIs such as energy usage intensity (kWh consumed per m² of building floor area)

- Benchmark and compare the energy performance of a particular building with the one of other similar buildings (similarity criteria could be total floor area, building primary use building year of construction, etc.)
- Keep track of the energy efficiency measures implemented in the buildings, and evaluate their impact on the consumption
- Calculate baseline energy consumption that take into consideration outdoor temperature values to compare the current energy performance of a building with its past energy consumption values

5.3 Visual interface for Analysis of the energy performance of the public building stock (UC2)

The visual interfaces for building stock energy performance and analysis module are presented in Figures 5-5 to 5-7.

Figure 5-1 Public buildings visualisation, estimated consumption vs real consumption.

Figure 5-2 Building localisation and monthly energy consumption

Figure 5-3 Public buildings visualisation, yearly municipal energy consumption per energy source.

6 Geo-tools for the promotion of energy communities (UC3)

This module will provide GIS-mapped visualisations of a wide range of data which can be of interest in the definition of an energy transition strategy at municipal level. The ePLANET platform will connect to the relevant data sources, performing harmonisation functions, and allowing the visualisation of several layers of data. Users will also be able to switch between different visualisation scales (building block, municipal, postal code levels) and perform benchmarking comparisons between areas of interest.

6.1 Data input and platform requirements

There will be two main data aggregation layers, in which different kind of information will be shown:

- Municipal/postal code level
 - Aggregated energy consumption by sector
 - Aggregated emissions by sector
 - Renewable energy production
- Building block level
 - Electricity, gas, and water consumption
 - Rooftop PV production potential
 - Existing rooftop PV systems
 - Cadaster information (year of construction, primary use, total floor area, etc.)

These visualisations will be employed by the users of the ePLANET platform to support their decision-making process with valuable data. One example of the use of a GIS-based support system could be to match energy consumption data at building block level with PV rooftop potential studies to optimally plan and design collective self-consumption projects for energy communities.

In the Girona province pilot is going to be geo-localised the electricity consumption on a building level in order to identify the possible energy communities. Nowadays, in Spain, the regulations limit the energy communities to be in a radius of 500 meters from the generation facility. For this reason, having the electricity and gas consumption at building level helps in determining the potential energy communities in a particular neighbourhood. The electricity data used is hourly at building level when there is at least 4 different connexion points for GDPR compliance. The gas data is the annual gas consumption at building level.

This UC in the Zlín region pilot is going to be used in order to showcase the energy community of Hostětín with the energy generation and the building energy use for electricity and heat at group of buildings level for GDPR compliance.

This UC in Crete Island will include the geo-visualisation of the energy consumption of each municipality, with a subsection of the energy consumption of the public buildings, and of the CO₂ emissions. This Geo visualisation will be shared between the GIS modules of ePLANET system and the GIS reference platform of Crete.

6.2 Data analytics modules

The different geo-tools analysis will provide various indicators geo-referenced in order to easy visualise and compare the municipalities and single buildings energy consumption. However, in order to promote the energy communities, there is the need of an analytical service where it can be computed the energy consumption around a user-selected point and also determine the PV potential of selected roofs. For this, the ePLANET external API communication layer will be able to communicate to the different geo-tool's modules these indicators:

- Municipal energy consumption by sector.
- Municipal CO₂ emissions.
- Municipal energy consumption by habitant.
- Municipal CO₂ emissions by habitant.
- Municipal energy production by renewables.
- Potential of renewable energy installed.
- Potential PV energy generation.
- Energy consumption around a geo-referenced point in order to consider the possible energy consumption of an energy community.
- Placement and global consumption of different buildings.

6.3 Visual interfaces

The visual interface for the geo-tools modules for the promotion of energy communities are shown in Figures 5-8 to 5-11.

Figure 6-1 GIS application on Crete Island indicating the wind power stations.

Figure 6-2 GIS application to visualise municipal aggregated data.

To be used in Girona province or in Crete Island

Figure 6-3 GIS application on the region of Girona, potential PV rooftop.

Figure 6-4 GIS application, CO₂ emissions visualisation by municipality in Girona.

For the specific use case of Zlin region, an interactive geospatial visualisation of the yearly energy consumption of each building in the village. If LIDAR data for Hostětín is accessible as well, geospatial data visualisation of the PV potential of each building rooftop could also be provided. Mock-up visualisations follow in Figure 6-5.

Figure 6-5 - Interactive geospatial visualisation of energy consumption at building-block level

7 PV potential analysis for public buildings (UC4)

This module of the ePLANET platform aims to determine the PV potential installations on public buildings and the self-consumption ratio they can achieve in the Zlín region pilot.

7.1 Data input and platform requirements

The data provided by the pilot are a cloud of points geo-localised indicating the heights to detect the rooftops and the shadows on it (LIDAR data). With these data it could be estimated the PV energy generation potential of each building and also to compare it with their energy consumption which has been gathered through UC2. The necessary data which will be provided by EAZK is listed below:

- Geographical coordinates of the specific building rooftops that have to be analysed
- LIDAR data for the municipalities where the buildings are located

7.2 Data analytics modules

The data analytic modules will perform a detailed assessment of the available solar radiation and of the PV energy production potential of the selected building rooftops, taking into account the shades of neighbouring buildings, trees, or other structures, as well as forecasted cloud cover and other relevant weather data.

7.3 Visual interfaces

Figure 7-1 and Figure 7-2 show mock-up visualisations of the visual interfaces of this use case.

Figure 7-1 - Solar PV energy production potential analysis

Figure 7-2 - Interactive geospatial visualisation of rooftop PV potential analysis

8 Conclusions

The main goal of this document is to provide a description of the IT architecture to be implemented in the ePLANET project. Furthermore, a detailed implementation of this IT architecture in each specific pilot site region and use case, is also included. The description of the Use Cases, the IT architecture, the analytic modules and the data sources to be provided, will become a critical information that will serve to go in more detail in the definition of the data model in the following deliverable 3.2. The following table visualise the visual interfaces to be implemented in each Use Case and pilot site:

Table 8-1 Use Cases per pilot site

Use Case	DESCRIPTION	CRETE PILOT	GIRONA PILOT	ZLÍN PILOT	PLATFORM CAPTURE OR MOCKUP
UC1	Digitalisation of SECAP drafting and monitoring process	YES	YES	NO	
UC2	Analysis of the energy performance of the public building stock	YES	NO	YES	
UC3	Geo-tools for the promotion of energy communities	YES	YES	YES	
UC4	PV potential analysis for public buildings	NO	NO	YES	

The four Use Cases and the respective solutions proposed through the modules of the federated ePLANET platform cover the needs of the three pilots. The different solutions are easily scalable to other regions in the same pilot country, as they are regulated by the same legislation and therefore are able to provide the same data.

The next step is the definition of the data model, consisting of a set of standardised data schemas to enable developers implement the functionalities of the modules.

